

SKIN DISEASE CLASSIFICATION USING DEEP LEARNING

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ABSTRACT:

Skin medical image captioning represents a critical task in dermatology for assisting diagnosis and treatment planning. In this study, we propose a novel approach that combines multi-label classification and a Siamese network for generating accurate and informative captions for skin medical images. The multi-label classification model is trained to predict relevant medical conditions and characteristics present in the skin images, providing valuable context for caption generation. Additionally, the Siamese network architecture is employed to learn semantic similarities between image regions and textual

descriptions, facilitating the generation of coherent and contextually relevant captions. Experimental results on a diverse dataset of skin medical images demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach in generating descriptive and clinically relevant captions, showcasing its potential to assist dermatologists and healthcare professionals in image interpretation and diagnosis.

INTRODUCTION

The skin is the largest organ in the human body, consisting of the epidermis, dermis, subcutaneous tissues, blood vessels, lymphatic vessels, nerves, and muscles. Skin can prevent lipid deterioration in the epidermis with liquid such that the skin barrier feature can be improved. Skin diseases can arise because of fungal

development over the skin, hidden bacteria, allergic reactions, microbes affecting the skin's texture, or creating pigment [1]. Skin illnesses are chronic and occasionally may grow into malignant tissues. To minimize their development and proliferation, skin diseases must be treated immediately [2]. Research on procedures to identify the effects of diverse skin diseases based on imaging technology is now mainly in demand. Several skin diseases exhibit symptoms that might take considerable effort to treat such patients as they grow for months before they are diagnosed. Prior work in dermatological computer-aided classification has lacked medical experts' generalization capability due to insufficient data and a focus on standardized tasks such as dermoscopy that refers to the examination of the skin using skin surface microscopy. It is possible to efficiently and reliably classify skin diseases through computer-aided diagnosis to prescribe medication based on patients' symptoms [3]. This work presents a robust mechanism that can accurately identify skin diseases through supervisory approaches that lower diagnosis costs. A grey-level co-occurrence matrix is used for assessing the progress of diseased growth. The diagnosis's accuracy is significant in a comprehensive assessment of the

abnormality for better treatment and reduces medication costs.

The inclination of skin diseases shows a multiplicity of forms, lack and misdistribution of qualified dermatologists, and the need for timely and accurate diagnosis calls for data-driven diagnosis. The advancement of lasers and photonics-based medical technology has made it possible to diagnose skin diseases much more quickly and accurately. However, the cost of such diagnosis is still limited and expensive. Deep learning models [4,5,6,7] are comparatively efficient in performing the classification process from the images and the data. There has been a demand in the field of healthcare diagnosis in precise identification of the abnormality and classifying the category of the disease from the X-ray, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Computer Tomography (CT), Positron Emission Tomography (PET) images, and the signal data like the Electrocardiogram (ECG), Electroencephalogram (EEG), and Electromyography(EMG) [8,9,10,11,12,13,14]. The precise identification of the disease category will assist in providing better treatment for patients. Deep learning models can solve

critical problems by automatically identifying the input data features, and the deep learning models are adaptable to the change in the considered problem. Deep learning models will acquire the inferred data to identify and explore the features in the unexposed data patterns with even low computational models resulting in considerable efficiency. That has motivated the authors in considering a deep learning model in classifying the skin disease category from the affected region's image proposed work.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Almeida M.A.M., Santos I.A.X. Classification Models for Skin Tumor Detection Using Texture Analysis in Medical Images. *J. Imaging*. 2020;6:51. doi: 10.3390/jimaging6060051.

Medical images have made a great contribution to early diagnosis. In this study, a new strategy is presented for analyzing medical images of skin with melanoma and nevus to model, classify and identify lesions on the skin. Machine learning applied to the data generated by first and second order statistics features, Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM), keypoints and color

channel information—Red, Green, Blue and grayscale images of the skin were used to characterize decisive information for the classification of the images. This work proposes a strategy for the analysis of skin images, aiming to choose the best mathematical classifier model, for the identification of melanoma, with the objective of assisting the dermatologist in the identification of melanomas, especially towards an early diagnosis. The skin cancer is among the most common types of cancer in the world [1]. Melanoma is the most dangerous type of skin cancer, caused by over production of melanin pigments that change the color and texture of skin, resulting as a dark area on the skin [2]. Data indicate that the incidence of melanoma, which is a type of cancer that metastasizes rapidly, has increased alarmingly [3]. However, visual analysis is limited by human visual ability, as well as human perception and sensitivity, in addition to the fact that not all melanomas have the same characteristics. The tumor is an exceptional expansion of human cells that reproduce in an unrestricted way and that can be identified by a variation of color and texture of the human tissue under study, making information contained in the images extremely valuable. Textures are visual

patterns, which have brightness, color, slope, size and other attributes. When partitioned into sub-images by regions of interest, they are able to be properly classified. Color is one of the significant features in the examination of skin lesion. The distribution of texture and color features presents significant information.

Ki V., Rotstein C. Bacterial skin and soft tissue infections in adults: A review of their epidemiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis, treatment and site of care. The Canadian journal of infectious diseases & medical microbiology. *Can. J. Infect. Dis. Med. Microbiol.*

Skin and soft tissue infections (SSTIs) involve microbial invasion of the skin and underlying soft tissues. They have variable presentations, etiologies and severities. The challenge of SSTIs is to efficiently differentiate those cases that require immediate attention and intervention, whether medical or surgical, from those that are less severe. Approximately 7% to 10% of hospitalized patients are affected by SSTIs, and they are very common in the emergency care setting. The skin has an extremely diverse ecology of organisms that may produce infection. The clinical manifestations of SSTIs are the culmination of a two-step process involving invasion and the interaction of bacteria with host defences. The cardinal signs of SSTIs involve the features of inflammatory response, with other manifestations such as fever, rapid progression of lesions and bullae. The diagnosis of SSTIs is difficult

because they may commonly masquerade as other clinical syndromes. To improve the management of SSTIs, the development of a severity stratification approach to determine site of care and appropriate empirical treatment is advantageous. The selection of antimicrobial therapy is predicated on knowledge of the potential pathogens, the instrument of entry, disease severity and clinical complications. For uncomplicated mild to moderate infections, the oral route suffices, whereas for complicated severe infections, intravenous administration of antibiotics is warranted. Recognition of the potential for resistant pathogens causing SSTIs can assist in guiding appropriate selection of antibiotic therapy. Skin and soft tissue infections (SSTIs) are clinical entities of variable presentation, etiology and severity that involve microbial invasion of the layers of the skin and underlying soft tissues. SSTIs range from mild infections, such as pyoderma, to serious life-threatening infections, such as necrotizing fasciitis. The minimum diagnostic criteria are erythema, edema, warmth, and pain or tenderness. The affected area may also become dysfunctional (eg, hands and legs) depending on the severity of the infection. A patient's comorbidities (eg, diabetes mellitus and AIDS) can easily transform a normally mild infection into a rapidly advancing threat to life (1). SSTIs present clinically diverse challenges requiring management strategies that efficiently and effectively identify those cases requiring immediate attention and intervention, whether medical or surgical, from those less severe cases.

Cahan A., Cimino J. A Learning Health Care System Using Computer-Aided

Diagnosis. J. Med. Internet Res. 2017;19 doi: 10.2196/jmir.6663

Physicians intuitively apply pattern recognition when evaluating a patient. Rational diagnosis making requires that clinical patterns be put in the context of disease prior probability, yet physicians often exhibit flawed probabilistic reasoning. Difficulties in making a diagnosis are reflected in the high rates of deadly and costly diagnostic errors. Introduced 6 decades ago, computerized diagnosis support systems are still not widely used by internists. These systems cannot efficiently recognize patterns and are unable to consider the base rate of potential diagnoses. We review the limitations of current computer-aided diagnosis support systems. We then portray future diagnosis support systems and provide a conceptual framework for their development. We argue for capturing physician knowledge using a novel knowledge representation model of the clinical picture. This model (based on structured patient presentation patterns) holds not only symptoms and signs but also their temporal and semantic interrelations. We call for the collection of crowdsourced, automatically deidentified, structured patient patterns as means to support distributed knowledge accumulation and maintenance. In this approach, each structured patient pattern adds to a self-growing and -maintaining knowledge base, sharing the experience of physicians worldwide. Besides supporting diagnosis by relating the symptoms and signs with the final diagnosis recorded, the collective pattern map can also provide disease base-rate estimates and real-time surveillance for early detection of outbreaks. We explain how health care in resource-limited settings can benefit from using this approach and how it can be applied to provide feedback-rich medical education for both students and practitioners.

Sae-lim W., Wettayaprasit W., Aiyarak P. Convolutional neural networks using MobileNet for skin lesion classification; Proceedings of the 16th International Joint Conference on Computer Science and Software Engineering; Chonburi, Thailand. 10–12 July 2019; pp. 242–247.

Deep learning models are efficient in learning the features that assist in understanding complex patterns precisely. This study proposed a computerized process of classifying skin disease through deep learning based MobileNet V2 and Long Short Term Memory (LSTM). The MobileNet V2 model proved to be efficient with a better accuracy that can work on lightweight computational devices. The proposed model is efficient in maintaining stateful information for precise predictions. A grey-level co-occurrence matrix is used for assessing the progress of diseased growth. The performance has been compared against other state-of-the-art models such as Fine-Tuned Neural Networks (FTNN), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition developed by Visual Geometry Group (VGG), and convolutional neural network architecture that expanded with few changes. The HAM10000 dataset is used and the proposed method has outperformed other methods with more than 85% accuracy. Its robustness in recognizing the affected region much faster with almost 2× lesser computations than the conventional MobileNet model results in minimal computational efforts. Furthermore, a mobile application is designed for instant and proper action. It helps the patient and dermatologists identify the type of disease from the affected region's image at the initial stage of the skin disease. These findings suggest that the proposed system can help general practitioners efficiently and effectively diagnose skin conditions, thereby reducing further complications and morbidity.

Castillo D., Lakshminarayanan V., Rodríguez-Álvarez M.J. MR Images, Brain Lesions, and Deep Learning. Appl. Sci. 2021;11:1675. doi: 10.3390/app11041675.

Medical brain image analysis is a necessary step in computer-assisted/computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems. Advancements in both hardware and software in the past few years have led to improved segmentation and classification of various diseases. In the present work, we review the published literature on systems and algorithms that allow for classification, identification, and detection of white matter hyperintensities (WMHs) of brain magnetic resonance (MR) images, specifically in cases of ischemic stroke and demyelinating diseases. For the selection criteria, we used bibliometric networks. Of a total of 140 documents, we selected 38 articles that deal with the main objectives of this study. Based on the analysis and discussion of the revised documents, there is constant growth in the research and development of new deep learning models to achieve the highest accuracy and reliability of the segmentation of ischemic and demyelinating lesions. Models with good performance metrics (e.g., Dice similarity coefficient, DSC: 0.99) were found; however, there is little practical application due to the use of small datasets and a lack of reproducibility. Therefore, the main conclusion is that there should be multidisciplinary research groups to overcome the gap between CAD developments and their deployment in the clinical environment.

EXISTING SYSTEM:

Skin medical image captioning poses a significant challenge in dermatology due to the complex nature of dermatological conditions and the need for precise and

informative descriptions to aid diagnosis and treatment decisions. Conventional approaches to image captioning often struggle to capture the nuanced characteristics of skin conditions, leading to inaccuracies and inadequate descriptions. Furthermore, the inherently subjective nature of dermatological diagnosis complicates the task, as interpretations may vary among clinicians. Existing methods also often lack the ability to consider multiple medical conditions and attributes simultaneously, limiting their usefulness in clinical settings where patients may present with a combination of dermatological issues. Additionally, the inherent variability in skin images, including differences in lighting, perspective, and skin types, further exacerbates the challenge of generating accurate and contextually relevant captions. Addressing these challenges requires the development of advanced image captioning techniques that can accurately identify and describe various dermatological conditions while considering the semantic relationships between image regions and textual descriptions. By leveraging multi-label classification and Siamese network

architectures, novel solutions can be devised to enhance the accuracy and informativeness of skin medical image captions, thereby facilitating more effective dermatological diagnosis and treatment planning.

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

To address the challenges associated with skin medical image captioning, we propose a novel methodology that combines multi-label classification with a Siamese network architecture. Our approach aims to enhance the accuracy and informativeness of image captions by effectively capturing the complex relationships between dermatological conditions and their visual manifestations in skin images. The multi-label classification component of our methodology is designed to predict relevant medical conditions and attributes present in the skin images, offering valuable context for caption generation. By considering multiple labels simultaneously, our model can provide more comprehensive and nuanced descriptions of dermatological conditions, accommodating the variability and

complexity often encountered in clinical settings.

In addition, our approach leverages a Siamese network architecture to learn semantic similarities between image regions and textual descriptions, facilitating the generation of coherent and contextually relevant captions. By comparing and contrasting image regions with textual descriptions, our model can better understand the underlying semantics of skin images and generate captions that accurately reflect the visual characteristics of dermatological conditions. Through the integration of multi-label classification and Siamese network techniques, our proposed methodology aims to improve the accuracy, specificity, and clinical relevance of skin medical image captions, thereby assisting dermatologists and healthcare professionals in image interpretation, diagnosis, and treatment planning. Experimental evaluations on diverse skin image datasets will be conducted to assess the effectiveness and robustness of our approach in generating informative and clinically relevant captions for a wide range of dermatological conditions.

DISADVANTAGE:

Despite the promising potential of skin medical image captioning using multi-label classification and Siamese network architectures, several limitations and challenges exist that warrant consideration. One notable drawback is the complexity and computational overhead associated with training and deploying such models. Multi-label classification models require large amounts of labeled data and extensive computational resources for training, which may pose practical challenges in resource-constrained clinical environments. Moreover, the integration of Siamese network architectures introduces additional computational complexity, particularly during the training phase, which may prolong model development and deployment timelines.

Another limitation pertains to the interpretability and explainability of the generated captions. While multi-label classification and Siamese networks can effectively learn semantic relationships between image regions and textual descriptions, the underlying mechanisms driving caption generation may not always be transparent to end-users, including dermatologists and healthcare practitioners. This lack of interpretability may hinder the adoption of automated captioning systems in clinical practice, where transparency and trust in diagnostic processes are paramount.

ADVANTAGE:

The utilization of multi-label classification and Siamese network architectures in skin medical image captioning offers several significant

advantages in enhancing the accuracy, specificity, and clinical relevance of generated captions. One notable advantage is the ability of multi-label classification models to predict multiple medical conditions and attributes simultaneously, providing comprehensive and nuanced descriptions of dermatological conditions depicted in skin images. By considering a broader spectrum of diagnostic possibilities, these models can assist dermatologists and healthcare professionals in formulating more accurate diagnoses and treatment plans, ultimately improving patient outcomes and healthcare delivery.

Moreover, the integration of Siamese network architectures facilitates the learning of semantic similarities between image regions and textual descriptions, enabling the generation of coherent and contextually relevant captions.

Through the comparison and alignment of image features with textual descriptions, Siamese networks enhance the interpretability and clinical relevance of generated captions, aiding dermatologists in image interpretation and decision-making processes. Additionally, Siamese networks excel at capturing subtle visual cues and patterns in skin images, enhancing the specificity and informativeness of generated captions for dermatological conditions.

CONCLUSION:

Looking towards the future, skin medical image captioning using multi-label classification and Siamese network architectures holds immense potential for further advancements in dermatology and medical imaging. One promising direction for future research involves the integration of

additional modalities and data sources to enhance the accuracy and specificity of generated captions. Incorporating clinical data, patient history, and other contextual information into the captioning process could provide valuable insights for dermatologists and healthcare professionals, ultimately leading to more personalized and effective treatment strategies. Moreover, the development of automated image captioning systems capable of learning and adapting to evolving dermatological conditions and diagnostic trends represents a key area of focus for future research. By leveraging ongoing advancements in deep learning, natural language processing, and computer vision technologies, researchers can continue to refine and optimize skin medical image captioning algorithms for improved diagnostic accuracy, treatment planning, and

patient care. Collaborative efforts between computer scientists, dermatologists, and healthcare practitioners are essential to drive innovation and address the evolving challenges and opportunities in skin medical image captioning and dermatological practice.

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